

CHANGES IN THE PARAMETERS OF DAILY MONITORING OF BLOOD PRESSURE IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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Abstract.

Patients with arterial hypertension with altered indicators of the left atrium were studied The purpose of the study: to study the features of the parameters of daily arterial pressure monitoring during left atrium remodeling in a group of people with arterial hypertension. The examination of patients aged 30 to 56 years with arterial hypertension and cardiac arrhythmia was carried out. The patients were divided into two groups: group 1 – patients with hypertension without cardiac arrhythmias. Group 2 - these are patients with both hypertension and cardiac arrhythmia. Daily blood pressure was monitored and the relationship with left atrium remodeling was found. Predictors of cardiac arrhythmia in morphofunctional remodeling of the left atrium have been determined.

Key words.

cardiac arrhythmias, AF, essential hypertension, LV remodeling, left atrial stunning.

ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ ПАРАМЕТРОВ СУТОЧНОГО МОНИТОРИРОВАНИЯ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОГО ДАВЛЕНИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ

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Резюме.

Исследованы пациенты с артериальной гипертензией измененными показателями левого предсердия. Цель исследования: изучить особенности параметров суточного мониторинга артериального давления при ремоделировании левого предсердия в группе лиц с артериальной гипертензией. Проведено обследование пациентов в возрасте от 30 до 56 лет с артериальной гипертензией и нарушением сердечного ритма. Пациенты разделены на две группы: 1 группа – пациенты с гипертонической болезнью без нарушений сердечного ритма. 2 группа - это пациенты как с гипертонической болезнью с нарушением сердечного ритма. Было проведено мониторинг суточного артериального давления и найдена взаимосвязь с ремоделирование левого предсердия. Определены предикторы нарушения ритма сердца при морфофункциональном ремоделировании левого предсердия.

Ключевые слова.

суточное мониторирование артериального давления, нарушения ритма сердца, гипертоническая болезнь, ремоделирование левого предсердия.

Relevance: Changes in the heart that occur with arterial hypertension is the cause of the development of cardiac arrhythmias of ventricular extrasystoles (PVCs), tachycardia, atrial fibrillation. Structural changes in the atria such as "stunnedness" or stunning of the myocardium are of particular importance for the development of tachycardia, PVC, AF [4]. A natural consequence of arterial hypertension (AH) is the formation of left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), which leads to an increase in left ventricular rigidity and worsening of its diastolic relaxation, which leads to LV diastolic dysfunction [1,2,3].

G.K. Moe et al concluded that any increase in the size of the left atrium (LA) increases the likelihood of developing various rhythm disturbances [14, 22]. And in 1986 M.S. Kushakovsky described dilatation of the left atrium as a prerequisite for the inevitability of atrial fibrillation [5, 6]. It is known that atrial myocardial dystrophy with their subsequent "primary" and "secondary" (retrograde) expansion create a substrate for sinus rhythm disturbances (SR). However, earlier, in 1949, E. Phillip and S. Levin reported on the possibility of developing paroxysms of

tachycardia, atrial fibrillation (AF) in people who do not have any heart disease, except for the tachyarrhythmia itself.

It is known that in hypertension, remodeling of the left ventricle (LV) develops, including the processes of hypertrophy and dilatation, changes in geometry and impairment of systolic and diastolic functions [7,13]. Structural changes in the LV are accompanied by LA overload and its dilatation, which, in turn, is a factor predisposing to the development of rhythm disturbances. On the other hand, this rhythm disturbance itself causes LA dilatation [8,9,10].

However, recent research data indicate that a more accurate marker of LA structural remodeling is the LAI Volume Index (LAVI) [10, 11].

In 1989 W. Manning et al. demonstrated in their studies that in most patients with persistent AF, after restoration of sinus rhythm, a phenomenon of temporary mechanical LA dysfunction was observed, characterized by the authors as the phenomenon of "stunning" or "stunning" [16]. And in subsequent studies by other authors, the phenomenon of inhibition of the function of the LA and its ear was confirmed [17, 15, 5].

The inclusion of thiotriazoline in the complex of treatment of patients with supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias of medium grades (II-III classes according to B. Lown) contributed to a decrease in the phenomena of electrical instability of the myocardium and a significant antiarrhythmic effect. With good tolerability of the drug, thiotriazoline is 85.9% and 69.3% with ELE and PVC, respectively [19,20].

The examined patients showed early signs of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, while in patients after suffering an infectious respiratory disease, diastolic dysfunction is mainly represented by hemodynamic disorders and early stunning of the left atrium (67%) [18, 20, 21,22].

In the mosaic lesion of the myocardium, there are areas without signs of mechanical activity, but with preserved basic physiological functions. Deviation from this ideal geometry dictates the need for early application of diagnostic methods for the "dormant", "stunned" myocardium of the left atrium.

Purpose of the study: to study the features of heart rhythm disturbances in left atrial stunning in the early stages of left ventricular remodeling in patients with essential hypertension.

изучить особенности параметров суточного мониторинга артериального давления при ремоделировании левого предсердия в группе лиц с артериальной гипертензией.

Research methods: On the basis of the regional cardiological dispensary, a retrospective study of 85 outpatient records of patients with essential hypertension and rhythm disturbances at the age of 30 to 56 years (mean age 40.2 ± 2.7 years) was carried out. The observation period was 6 months. Patients complained of palpitations, recurrent discomfort behind the breastbone, feeling short of breath, and destabilization of blood pressure. An ultrasound examination (ECHOKG) was performed.

Standard echocardiography with the determination of the left ventricular mass index, as well as the relative thickness of the posterior wall of the left ventricle and the interventricular septum, makes it possible to characterize the geometry of the left ventricle, diffuse thickening of the myocardial walls due to interstitial edema, the size of the left atrium, the volume of the left atrium, the peak velocities of the early and late diastolic streams.

When assessing the geometric structure of the LV in the B-mode, the thickness of the anterior, septal, posterior and lateral LV walls in diastole was measured from the parasternal approach along the short axis at the level of the MV valves and papillary muscles. The anteroposterior size of the papillary muscles was determined from the position of the LV short axis in the parasternal projection. In the M-mode, the thickness of the interventricular septum and the posterior wall of the LV in diastole, the end diastolic size and the End systolic size of the LV, anteroposterior LA size, in 4 projections, in 2 projections were measured.

In order to diagnose left ventricular (LV) remodeling, the myocardial mass, myocardial mass index, and relative wall thickness index were determined. To assess the geometric model of the LV, we used the classification (normal LV geometry, concentric left ventricular remodeling - EDS, concentric LV hypertrophy - eccentric LV hypertrophy).

The patients were divided into 2 groups: group 1 - control group ($n = 38$) with hypertension without heart rhythm disturbances. The duration of hypertension was 4.794 ± 2.31 years, in group 2 ($n = 47$) with essential hypertension and cardiac arrhythmias - tachycardia, AF, PVC, impaired repolarization of the ventricles. The duration of hypertension in this group was 5.920 ± 3.21 years. In the presented group, during the study, we identified the following variants of cardiac arrhythmias: tachycardia - 10 (21%), frequent ventricular monotopic extrasystole - 18 (38%), polytopic - 6 (13%), atrial fibrillation - 13 (28%).

Statistical processing of the results was carried out using the statistical package "Statisticav.6.0". The arithmetic mean (M) and the error of the mean (m) were calculated. The normality of the sample distribution was assessed by the

Kolmogorov - Smirnov test. The reliability of the differences between the values was determined using the Student's t-test with a normal distribution of the trait, with the distribution of a trait different from normal - using the nonparametric Mann - Whitney method. For the analysis of qualitative features, Fisher's exact test and χ^2 were used. Differences were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Research results. Indicators of systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) in patients in group 2 were relatively higher, i.e. by 8.7% and 12.7% ($p < 0.05$), in relation to patients of group 1 of the study.

In the present work, we have revealed normal LV myocardial hypertrophy in the 1st group was found in 3.1%, in the 2nd group in 4.8%. Changes in geometry among hypertensive patients without cardiac arrhythmias were found in the largest number of patients with concentric myocardial remodeling - 21.9% (Pic. 1).

Note: CG-concentric remodeling, CG-concentric hypertrophy, EG-eccentric hypertrophy, NG-normal hypertrophy.

In the group of patients with essential hypertension and cardiac arrhythmias, persons with concentric LV hypertrophy (39%) ($n = 16$) dominated, while concentric remodeling was observed in 29.3% ($n = 12$). Eccentric hypertrophy 21.9% ($n = 9$).

In the diagnosis of left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) in patients with arterial hypertension (AH), the main method today is echocardiography (EchoCG). The role of electrocardiography (ECG) has recently diminished somewhat.

Table 1

Hemodynamic indices in the examined persons

No	Studied	Group 1-group	2-group n = 38
1	EDS, mm	53,202±3,340	54,432±4,286
2	ESS, mm	32,142±4,400	36,152±5,340
3	EDV , ml	118,020±12,730	128,126±10,643*
4	ESV , ml	31,711±16,786	36,786±18,412
5	IVS, mm	11,074±1,224	12,2400±3,033
6	BW LV, mm	10,348±2,330	12,029±2,785
7	Volume LA (ml)	41,711±16,654	46,786±18,321
8	LA long axis	4,161±3,340	4,712±3,230
9	EF LV, %	63,256±9,372	58,468±6,282*
10	MMLV (B- mode), g	213,136±6,467	285,115±5,128**
11	IMMLV, r/M ²	98,297±9,088	168,125±7,550**
	SBP	124,210±6,210	134,424±11,400*
	DBP	83,860±6,120	94,125±8,240*

Note: * p <0.05, ** p <0.05 significance of differences between groups

However, due to its general availability, technological simplicity, speed of obtaining information and the possibility of a parallel assessment of the state of the coronary circulation, this method cannot be “set aside”.

In our studies, according to echocardiography data, significant changes were only in EDV, EF, LVMM and LVMI. Indices of EDV by 9%, LVM by 34% and LVMI by 71% were higher in the group of patients with grade 1 hypertension. and heart rhythm disturbances, the LVEF is 9% lower in relation to patients with hypertension 1 tbsp. without heart rhythm disturbance.

In the study, data were obtained where, in persons with grade 1 hypertension without heart rhythm disturbances, in 35% of cases, an excess of IVS thickness of more than 11 mm was determined, and insignificant changes in the left atrium were also observed - 21%.

In 45% of the subjects, changes were observed both in the posterior and in the interventricular septum - changes in the volume of the left atrium were moderate in 19%. In 20% of cases, the IVS and the posterior wall of the left ventricle remained unchanged. In patients with hypertension 1 tbsp. with cardiac arrhythmias in 42% of cases, the thickness of the IVS exceeded the norm in 12%, where cardiac arrhythmias were often accompanied - the volume of the left atrium exceeded the

norm in 38% of cases. In 49%, changes were observed in the IVS and the posterior wall of the LV.

When analyzing the results of DMBP in persons with grade 1 hypertension without cardiac arrhythmias, SBP normotension was recorded in 22 individuals (68.7%), stable SBP hypertension was detected in 6 (18.7%), labile AH - in 2 (6.3%) individuals, labile hypotension of SBP was detected in 2 (6.3%) individuals.

According to the degree of SBP reduction at night, persons - "dippers" were 11 (42.3%) people, "non-dippers" - 4 (15.8%) persons. In terms of the degree of DBP reduction, "dippers" accounted for 9 (34.6%) patients, persons with an excessive decrease in DBP ("overdipper") - 2 (7.6%) persons.

In persons with grade 1 hypertension with cardiac arrhythmias in the group, SBP normotensiveness was registered in 7 individuals (17.1%), stable SBP hypertension was detected in 21, which amounted to 51.2%, labile - in 13 (31.7%) individuals.

In persons with grade 1 hypertension with cardiac arrhythmias, the groups with a sufficient decrease in SBP during sleep ("dipper") amounted to 8 (21.7%) persons, patients with an insufficient decrease in SBP ("non-dipper") - 2 (5, 2%), with nocturnal hypertension - 1 (2.6%) patient. According to the degree of DBP reduction at night, dipper faces accounted for 8 (21.7%) patients, non-dipper faces - 3 (7.8%) patients.

In individuals from the general groups, SBP normotension was registered in 29 individuals (39.7%), stable SBP hypertension was detected in 27, which was 37.0%, labile - in 15 (20.5%) individuals, labile SBP hypotension was detected in 2 (2.8%) individuals.

According to the degree of SBP reduction, "dippers" accounted for 41 (56%) patients, "non-dippers" - 28 (40%) patients, "night pickers" - 5 (5.2%) patients.

According to the degree of DBP reduction, "dippers" were 44 (61%) individuals, "non-dippers" and "over-dippers" - 13 (18%) and 8 (21%) individuals, respectively.

Thus, the approach to assessing LV diastolic dysfunction should be complex, including the study of the contractile and pumping functions of the myocardium, which in hypertension is manifested by remodeling of the left ventricle and stunning of the left atrium, but also by changes in the electrophysiological properties of cardiomyocytes. Ultrasound techniques used to assess left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with concentric hypertrophy and left atrial stanning can stratify the risk of developing atrial fibrillation.

Violation of the daily BP profile of the non-dipper type manifests itself already at the earliest stages and was more common in patients of group 2. An insufficient nighttime decrease in blood pressure occurs due to the phenomenon of increased activity of the sympathetic nervous system at night.

Essential hypertension is a significant, potentially modifiable risk factor for cardiac arrhythmias leading to remodeling "stunning" - stunning left atrial myocardium.

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